

Polarographic Study of Metal-Humic Acid Interaction. Determination of Stability Constants of Cd- and Zn-Humic Acid Complexes at Different pH

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Polarographic method has been successfully applied to study the interaction of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} with humic acids of two different sources in the pH range 4.0 to 6.0 in the presence of 0.1 (M) KNO_3 . The logarithms of stability constants range from 3.55 to 4.71 for Zn-humic acid and 3.25 to 3.93 for Cd-humic acid water-soluble complexes and vary little with the degree of saturation of the humic acid sites. It is also found that under the present experimental conditions 1 : 1 type of complex is formed.

THE availability of micronutrients to plants is strongly influenced by complexing with humus materials^{1,2}. Many attempts have been made to study the nature and the extent of this type of interaction. Interest has also been stimulated to study the complexation of toxic heavy metals with soils and sediments which are undoubtedly posing problems of environmental pollution. Methods used so far in this field for studying the stability of the metal complexes in terms of stability or formation constant have been mainly : the ion exchange equilibrium method³⁻⁹ of Schubert¹⁰ as simplified by Martell and Calvin¹¹, the potentiometric method^{12, 13} and the spectrophotometric method^{14, 8, 9}. Recently, a good number of workers^{15, 8, 16} have reviewed the use of Schubert's ion exchange equilibrium method as used in these cases and adversely criticised its limitations from different view points. The criticism is mainly due to the consideration of MCh_b — type of complex, but in their opinion the complex is presumably of M_aCh —type where $a \geq 1$. Thus, it seems that like metal-protein or metal-nucleic acid complexes, the humic acid molecule acts as the central group and the metal ions as ligand. In a recent publication, MacCarthy *et al.*¹⁷ criticised the use of Job's method of continuous variation, for the highly complicated structure and heterogeneity of humic acid molecules and concluded that studies of complexes in terms of stoichiometry and thermodynamic stability constants were hardly possible.

Tanford¹⁸, Saroff *et al.*¹⁹, Rao and Lal²⁰ and Miller *et al.*²¹ used polarographic technique to study the complexing of metal ions with proteins, nucleic acids, etc. utilizing the decrease in diffusion current of the metal ions after complex formation with high molecular weight substrates. Such a polarographic technique can be successfully applied to the investigation of metal—humic acid interaction, where the decrease in diffusion current is due to smaller value

of diffusion coefficient of the complex. But to our knowledge, no systematic attempt has so far been made in this respect.

In the present paper an attempt has been made to study quantitatively the interaction of Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+} with alcohol insoluble soil and peat humic acids in terms of stability constants of soluble, site-bound complexes at pH 4.0, 5.0 and 6.0 in the presence of 0.1 (M) KNO_3 . This determination of stability constants is based on the decrease in diffusion current of the metal ion resulting from the decrease in diffusion coefficient after complex formation.

Method : When a reducible ion of concentration C interacts with a substrate having concentration S, the average number of reducible ions bound to each substrate molecule is $\frac{\alpha C}{S}$, α being the fraction of the reducible ions bound to the substrate. The number of electrons necessary to discharge all the reducible ions bound to a substrate molecule is $\frac{\alpha n C}{S}$, where 'n' is the number of electrons needed to discharge each reducible ion. Again, as the metal-humic acid system slowly attains equilibrium compared to the droptime, the reduction of free and bound metals may be assumed to take place as two separate entities. Thus, the polarographic diffusion current I_d of such an equilibrium system is given by the Ilkovic equation of the form,

$$I_d = K_n (1-\alpha) CD_0^{0.5} + K_n \frac{\alpha C}{S} \cdot S \cdot D_s^{0.5}$$

where $K = 607 m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$; D_0 is the diffusion coefficient of free metal; D_s the diffusion coefficient of the bound metal; and m and t have their usual

* 0.1 N KCl may also be used, as trial experiments show.

meanings. Now if I_{d_0} is the diffusion current for the metal ions when all the ions are free then,

$$\frac{I_d}{I_{d_0}} = \frac{(1-\alpha)C + \alpha C \left(\frac{D_b}{D_0}\right)^{0.5}}{C} = \frac{C_f + X C_b}{C}$$

where $\alpha C = C_b$ = concentration of bound metal,
 $(1-\alpha) C = C_f$ = concentration of free metal,

and $\left(\frac{D_b}{D_0}\right)^{0.5} = X$ is a constant.

In a system where factors such as adsorption on mercury surface and viscosity do not appreciably affect the diffusion current, the ratio I_d/I_{d_0} can be taken as a measure of the extent of binding of metal ions to the substrate¹⁹. Once X is determined, C_f and C_b at equilibrium can be easily obtained knowing the values of I_d/I_{d_0} and C, where $C = C_f + C_b$.

The method is applicable to systems where irreversible or reversible diffusion controlled reduction occurs.

Now, considering the complex formation of metal ions with the complexing sites of humic acid and assuming that the binding at one site is independent of whether the adjacent site is occupied or not i. e., in the absence of co-operative effect, one may write the formation constant K as

$$K = \frac{\text{Concentration of occupied sites}}{\text{Concentration of unoccupied sites} \times \text{Concentration of free metal}}$$

$$\text{for } 1:1 \text{ type of complex i. e., } K = \frac{C_b}{(C_p - C_b) C_f}$$

where C_p is the concentration of total complexing sites in moles/lit., C_b and C_f are the molarities of bound and free metal ions respectively.

Experimental :

Humic acid was extracted from the forest soil (0-15 cm. depth) of Darjeeling district by standard alkali extraction procedure using 0.3 (M) NaOH solution at room temperature. Humic acid was separated by coagulating it with HCl at pH 2 and discarding the acid soluble fulvic acid. The humic acid was redissolved in NaOH solution and was coagulated again. The process was repeated until the supernatant showed a very faint colour of fulvic acid. Humic acid was further purified by extensive dialysis against distilled water by 'dializer tubing' (Arthur H. Thomas Co.); this permitted the passage of materials having molecular weight lower than 12,000. The alcohol soluble humatomelanic acid was then separated by 95% ethanol in a soxhlet apparatus. Dry humic acid was dissolved in NaOH solution, coagulated by HCl and then dialysed

again. Peat humic acid was taken from the sample supplied by Fluka A. G. and purified as above. The ash-contents were minimized by repeated treatment with cation exchange resin, Amberlite IR-120, saturated with hydrogen ion. Chemicals of analytical grade and distilled water were used in the present investigation. All metals were taken as nitrate salts for their high solubility and almost null power to coordinate to metals. The polarograms were recorded with a dc polarograph (Radelkis OH 102) coupled with a dropping Hg-electrode (droptime 4.2 sec) as cathode and a saturated calomel electrode as anode. Radelkis precision pH meter OP-205 was employed for pH measurement. At first, the pH of each type of humic acid was adjusted to 7.0 and it was diluted so as to make the colloid content 0.2 gm per 100 ml and kept as stock solution. The equilibrium study was performed at pH 4.0, 5.0 and 6.0 for both Cd and Zn ions. The pH's of the solutions of humic acids were found to change on standing in the presence of metal ion, so the equilibrium pH was adjusted as follows :

In a number of 25 ml beakers various quantities of humic acid (2 mg to 14 mg) were taken and appropriate amount of $Zn(NO_3)_2$ or $Cd(NO_3)_2$ solution and KNO_3 solution were added so that the final strength of the metal ions became 0.9×10^{-4} (M) and strength of KNO_3 0.1 (M). The pH's of the solutions were adjusted by careful addition of very dilute KOH or KNO_3 solutions and these were kept for 5 hours with occasional stirring. The pH of each set of solutions was again adjusted. Finally, the volume was made up to 25 ml in volumetric flask after 5 hours, the pH again was adjusted to appropriate value. The solutions were kept for another 12 hours in a thermostat at $28 \pm 0.5^\circ C$. The polarograms were recorded each time after bubbling pure nitrogen gas for 20 minutes. The pH's of the final equilibrium mixtures were recorded and found to be very close to the desired values.

Determination of X :

In different 'dializer tubings' various quantities of humic acids (7-15 mgs) were placed. 10 ml of 5.0×10^{-4} (M) metal ion solutions were added to each tubing and the solutions were dialysed against 30 ml of KNO_3 solution. Overall strength of KNO_3 was adjusted to 0.2 (M). Equilibrium was reached within 48 hours. Concentration of bound and free metal ions were calculated measuring the diffusion current of the external solution and X was computed from the following relationship :

$$X = \frac{I_d \text{ (internal)} - I_d \text{ (external)}}{I_{d_M}}$$

where I_{d_M} is the diffusion current for the same concentration of free metal ions which have been bound to the polyelectrolyte. Effects of Donnan potential were minimised by using high ionic

strength and the data were corrected for small volume change by osmosis.

Estimation of Complexing sites :

Metal ions ranging from 14 to 24m. moles were added to each of 20 ml of aliquots (40 mg of humic acids) contained in a number of stoppered bottles, followed by addition of KNO_3 solution to maintain their appropriate ionic strength. The pH 's of the solutions were adjusted to 4.0, 5.0 and 6.0 and the bottles were shaken for 6 hours. The pH was adjusted again and the volume of each set of solutions was made up to 50 ml in volumetric flasks which were then kept in a thermostat at $28 \pm 0.5^\circ$ with occasional shaking for 6 hours. The metal-humic acid complex was spun down by centrifugation (20,000 rpm) and the concentration of the metal ions in the supernatant was then estimated; the concentration of bound metal was thus calculated. On increasing the concentration of added metal the concentration of the bound metal ions slightly increased finally attaining a steady value in the metal ion uptake from which the concentration of the complexing sites in moles/lit of the stock solution was determined.

Results and Discussion

The present investigation reveals that complexing with humic acids causes small change in the reduction potential of the metal ion. This little change towards more negative potential is due to small negative free energy of combination¹⁸. As a result, in a solution where both free and bound metal ions are present, the reduction waves overlap producing a single wave somewhat flattened. For a metal-serum albumin system, Tanford¹⁹ added excess of the polyelectrolyte to the metal salt solution and plotted I_d/I_{d_0} against pH , wherefrom the limiting value of I_d/I_{d_0} was taken as X. However, in the interaction of Zn^{+2} and Cd^{+2} with bovine serum albumin, Rao and Lal²⁰ observed a variation in the value of X with pH of the solution and noted that this variation might be caused by the intrinsic and electrostatic factors. They, therefore, preferred the value of X for the particular pH , determined by an equilibrium dialysis technique. From our equilibrium dialysis experiment with soil humic acid, X has been found to be 0.20 for Zn and 0.202 for Cd ions. The values are almost identical for peat humic acids also. Again, the value of X here remains unchanged in the pH range 4.0 to 6.0 but decreases at higher pH . Attempts have also been made to determine the value of X from the plot of I_d/I_{d_0} vs pH at high humic acid concentration (Fig. 1). For Cd-humic acid systems, the values of I_d/I_{d_0} decrease with increasing pH and do not give a limiting value even at high pH . The I_d/I_{d_0} values for Zn-humic acid complexes at high humic acid concentration and beyond pH 7.0 could not be measured because the

Fig. 1. The ratio (i_d/I_{d_0}) as a function of pH for Cd-soil humic acid (O) and Cd-peat humic acid complex (●) in presence of 3.1(M) KNO_3 . Metal ion concentration = 0.9×10^{-4} (M) Soil humic acid concentration = 0.12gm/100ml Peat humic acid concentration = 0.18gm/100ml

metal ion reduced at slightly higher negative potential and the diffusing current of the metal merged with the kinetic current of the hydrogen ion reduction.

At high pH (above pH 6.0 for Cd^{+2} and Zn^{+2}); heavy metal ions probably form hydroxo-metal-humic acid complexes by the dissociation of H^+ from aquocomplex^{13,22}. As a result, at high pH the complex becomes negatively charged and the residual negative charge on the complex makes the bound metal ions unavailable at the electrode surface for reduction. This may be a possible cause for the decrease in the value of X at higher pH . Experiments with Cu^{+2} and Pb^{+2} (not shown in the present paper) also support this conjecture. For these metal ions which have been found to form hydroxo-complexes at relatively lower pH (4.5), the value of X tends to decrease at comparatively lower pH values than those for Cd^{+2} and Zn^{+2} . The same reason may be invoked to account for the continuous decrease observed in the value of I_d/I_{d_0} for Cd-humic acid system at a high concentration of humic acid, instead of its attaining a limiting value at high pH .

In table 2, log K values have been shown against the corresponding log (1- θ) values, where θ is the fraction of the total sites of humic acids occupied by the metal ions. It can be seen from the table that within the chosen concentration range the variation of log K with log (1- θ) is insignificantly small and somewhat random at any particular pH .

Thus it may be concluded that in the present experimental condition the assumption of 1 : 1 type of complex and absence of any larger co-operative effect is valid. Cd^{+2} and Zn^{+2} have been found to form fairly stable complexes with humic acids;

stability constants follow the Mellor and Maley series¹¹, the values increasing with increasing pH (see Table 2). The differences in the values of log K for peat and soil humic acids are not very significant, although soil humic acid gives larger values.

From Figs. 2 to 5 it clear that the interaction increases to a great extent as the pH of the solution is raised from 4.0 to 5.0 but this trend is less pronounced at a higher pH. This confirms the predominant role of the carboxylic acid groups in the

TABLE 1—MAXIMUM COMPLEXING ABILITY OF SOIL AND PEAT HUMIC ACIDS IN MILIMOLES/100 GM.

pH For Zn ²⁺ For Cd ²⁺	Soil humic acid			Peat humic acid		
	4.0	5.3	6.0	4.0	5.0	6.0
	55.15	94.36	133.58	60.35	102.10	150.00
	52.49	86.59	117.25	51.19	88.69	133.69

TABLE—2. LOG K AND CORRESPONDING LOG (1-θ) FOR COMPLEXES OF Zn²⁺ AND Cd²⁺ WITH SOIL AND PEAT HUMIC ACID

Zn-soil humic acid complex				Cd-soil humic acid complex			
Log (1-θ)	log K	Average log K	pH	log (1-θ)	log K	Average log K	pH
-0.1278	3.60			-0.0625	3.26		
-0.1205	3.66	3.62	4.0	-0.0591	3.26	3.25	4.0
-0.0922	3.62			-0.0536	3.24		
-0.0799	3.58			-0.0492	3.23		
-0.2960	4.47			-0.1213	3.64		
-0.2486	4.51	4.48	5.0	-0.1029	3.64	3.63	5.0
-0.2046	4.49			-0.0898	3.57		
-0.1709	4.47			-0.0780	3.64		
-0.3756	4.69			-0.1548	3.84		
-0.2562	4.64	4.71	6.0	-0.1380	3.96	3.93	6.0
-0.1959	4.66			-0.1260	3.90		
-0.1337	4.84			-0.0878	4.02		
Zn-peat humic acid complex				Cd-peat humic acid complex			
Log (1-θ)	log K	Average log K	pH	log (1-θ)	log K	Average log K	pH
-0.1152	3.53			-0.0711	3.33		
-0.1022	3.58	3.55	4.0	-2.0642	3.31	3.29	4.0
-0.0896	3.56			-0.0573	3.27		
-0.0773	3.52			-0.0506	3.23		
-0.1928	3.96			-0.0917	3.49		
-0.1484	3.98			-0.0853	3.53		
-0.1212	4.02	4.00	5.0	-0.0763	3.54	3.52	5.0
-0.0987	4.03			-0.0605	3.53		
-0.2747	4.42			-0.1219	3.56		
-0.1913	4.33	4.33	6.0	-0.0846	3.61	3.64	6.0
-0.1491	4.31			-0.0749	3.68		
-0.1020	4.26			-0.0635	3.69		

This indicates the similarity in complexing nature of both types of humic acids. The equilibrium studies above pH 6.0 have been avoided because of the possibility of hydrated metal oxide formation¹². Incidentally, it should be mentioned here that the polarographic method is applicable to systems where considerable amount of free and bound ions are present; the calculation of stability constants was therefore, not made at very low and high concentrations of humic acids in presence of fixed amount of metal ion.

complex formation because within this pH range the carboxylic acid groups are easily ionisable and become available for complex formation. Nevertheless, the contribution of phenolic-OH group, ionisable in this pH range, cannot be ignored.

Considering heterogeneity in the composition of humic acid, it may be noted that no two complexing sites in humic acid are precisely identical. Thus, the stability constant values obtained in this study should describe a weighted average value of different

Fig. 2. Plot of (I_d / I_{d_0}) vs. Conc. of humic acid for Zn-soil humic acid complex at pH 4.0, 5.0 and 6.0 in presence of 0.1(M) KNO_3 . Metal ion concentration = $0.9 \times 10^{-4}(M)$

Fig. 3. Plot of (I_d / I_{d_0}) Vs. Conc. of humic acid for Zn-peat humic acid complex at pH 4.0, 5.0 and 6.0 in presence of 0.1(M) KNO_3 . Metal ion concentration = $0.9 \times 10^{-4}(M)$.

Fig. 4. Plot of (I_d / I_{d_0}) Vs. Conc. of humic acid for Cd-Soil humic acid complex at pH 4.0, 5.0 and 6.0 in presence of 0.1(M) KNO_3 . Metal ion concentration $0.9 \times 10^{-4}(M)$

Fig. 5. Plot of (I_d / I_{d_0}) Vs. Conc. of humic acid for Cd-peat humic acid complex at pH 4.0, 5.0 and 6.0 in presence of 0.1(M) KNO_3 . Metal ion concentration = $0.9 \times 10^{-4}(M)$.

potential sites for the components of the system. The complex with bidentate sites may occur through phthalic (two adjacent -COOH gr.) or salicylic acid (one COOH and one OH in the adjacent position) type structure with the predominant role of the former giving 1 : 1 type of complex².

In a recent study, Stevenson¹³ suggested the possibility of 2 : 1 type of complexes at high site to metal ratio, where two bidentate ligands were attached to the same metal ion. This type of complex is, however, not formed in our experiments, which is evident from the following fact. The formation of 2 : 1 type of complex should result in a negative charge on the complex itself thereby making the bound metal ions unavailable at the electrode surface for reduction, as in the case of hydroxometal complexes. Thus, in the case of the formation of 2 : 1 type of complexes with increasing site to metal ratio, there would have been a continuous decrease in the value of I_d / I_{d_0} instead of showing any gradual constancy caused by the binding of apparently all the metal ions to the substrate. But in the present study, we observed that the value of I_d / I_{d_0} approached gradually and remained constant at the value close to X (0.20) (Fig 2 at pH 6.0) even when site to metal ratio was high indicating that all the metal ions were bound in the state of 1 : 1 type only.

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References.

1. J. F. HODGSON, *Adv. Agron.*, 1963, **15**, 119-159.
2. F. J. STEVENSON and M. S. ARDAKANI, Micronutrients in soil *Am. Soc. Agron. Inc.*, Madison, Wisc, 1972, pp. 79-114.
3. M. H. MILLER and A. J. OHLROGGE, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1958, **22**, 225-228.
4. N. S. RANDHAWA and F. E. BROADBENT. *Soil Sci.* 1965, **9**, 362-366.
5. C. COURPRON, *Ann. Agron.*, 1967, **18**, 623-638.
6. F. L. HIMES and S. A. BARBER, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1957, **21**, 368-373.
7. K. MATSUDA and M. IKUTA, *Soil Sci. Pant Nutre*, (Japan) 1969, **15**, 169-174.
8. M. SCHNITZER and E. H. HANSEN, *Soil Sci.*, 1970, **109**, 333-340.
9. M. SCHNITZER and S. I. M. SKINNER, *Soil Sci.*, 1967, **103**, 247-252.
10. J. SCHUBERT, *J. Phys. and Colloid Chem.*, 1948, **52**, 340-356.
11. A. E. MARTELL and M. Calvin. Chemistry of the metal chelate compounds. Prentice Hall, Inc., Englewood Cliffs, New York, 1952.
12. F. J. STEVENSON, S. A. KRASTANOV and M. S. ARDAKANI, *Geoderma*, 1973, **9**, 129-141.
13. F. J. STEVENSON, *Soil Sci.*, 1977, **123**, 10-17.
14. D. S. GAMBLE, M. SCHNITZER and I. HOFFMAN, *Cn. J. Chem.*, 1970, **48**, 3197-3204.
15. J. S. CLARK and R. C. TURNER, *Soil Sci.*, 1969, **107**, 8-11.
16. H. ZUNINO, G. GALINDO, P. PEIRANO and M. AGUILERA, *Soil Sci.*, 1972, **114**, 229-233
17. P. MACCARTHY and H. B. MARK. JR, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1976, 267-276.
18. C. TANFORD. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*. 1951, **73**, 2066-2070.
19. H. A. SAROFF and H. J. MARK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 1420, 1426,
20. M. S. N. RAO and H. LAL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3222-3226.
21. I. R. MILLER and D. BACH, *Biopolymers*, 1967, **5**, 161-172.
22. H. VAN DIJK, *Geoderma*, 1971, **5**, 53-67.